

1 Title:

2 Adaptations in common synaptic inputs to spinal motor neurons during grasping versus a less
3 functional hand task

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27 **Abstract**

28 Previous evidence suggests that shared synaptic inputs across spinal motor neurons play a key
29 role in coordinating multiple muscles during hand movements, reducing control complexity.
30 In this study, we investigated how the nervous system modulates these common synaptic inputs
31 during a functionally relevant grip (grasping) compared to less functionally relevant hand tasks.
32 Seventeen participants performed three different tasks: simultaneous four-finger flexion
33 without thumb involvement (four-finger flexion), thumb flexion, and simultaneous flexion of
34 both fingers and thumb (grasping). For each task, subjects sustained isometric contractions at
35 5% and 15% of maximal voluntary contraction, while high-density surface electromyograms
36 (HDsEMG) were recorded from the superficial extrinsic flexor muscles of the hand. Motor unit
37 spike trains were decomposed from HDsEMG and tracked across tasks, and their mean
38 discharge rate was calculated. Coherence between motor units was quantified within the delta,
39 alpha, and beta bands to estimate common synaptic oscillations. At both force levels, the mean
40 discharge rate decreased during grasping compared to four-finger flexion but increased during
41 grasping compared to thumb flexion. Additionally, the area under the curve of coherence
42 within the alpha band decreased by ~20% during grasping compared to the four-finger flexion
43 task, with no significant delta or beta bands changes. These reductions in alpha band coherence
44 were reflected in force oscillations, showing decreased force-neural drive coupling within the
45 alpha band and increased force steadiness during grasping compared to four-finger flexion.
46 Our findings suggest that a functionally relevant and frequently used grip involves distinct
47 neural control mechanisms that ultimately enhance force control.

48

49 **Keywords:**

50 Hand; neural control; motor unit; low-dimensional control

51 **Introduction**

52 The human hand is capable of performing a wide range of movements with remarkable
53 versatility, enabling complex interactions with the environment (Napier, 1956). While humans
54 possess some degree of finger individualization, most hand movements rely on the coordinated
55 flexion of multiple fingers, particularly for grasping, a fundamental action in daily activities
56 (Young, 2003, Alméjija et al., 2015, Schieber and Santello, 2004). The anatomical
57 specialization of the human hand, such as a fully opposable thumb, larger intrinsic muscles,
58 and the ability to arch the palm of the hand, supports the performance of prehensile movements,
59 allowing for efficient object manipulation (Napier, 1956, Napier, 1960, Napier, 1965, Marzke,
60 1997, Susman, 1979, Marzke and Shackley, 1986). Furthermore, the functional relevance of
61 grasping is evolutionarily evident from early development, as newborns display an instinctive
62 grasping reflex that later transitions into voluntary grasping, reinforcing its role as a
63 fundamental component of human motor behaviour (Dennis, 1943, Twitchell, 1965). Taken
64 together, these findings highlight that while humans exhibit some degree of independent finger
65 control, most everyday manual tasks, from tool use to object manipulation, rely on the
66 coordinated flexion of multiple digits, making grasping one of the most functionally relevant
67 hand movements.

68

69 Precision and dexterity during grasping require a finely coordinated interplay of the forces
70 produced by the multiple muscles controlling the fingers (Landsmeer, 1963, Long et al., 1970).
71 Rather than individually controlling each extrinsic hand muscle, the central nervous system
72 synergistically coordinates them, resulting in the required hand movement, which reduces the
73 degrees of freedom and, consequently, simplifies control (for review, see Santello et al.
74 (2013)). This modular control of fingers and hand movements, referred to as “hand synergies”,
75 has been extensively documented through different methodologies, including kinematic data

76 (Soechting and Flanders, 1997, Santello et al., 1998, Santello et al., 2002), force measurements
77 (Li et al., 1998, Reilly and Hammond, 2000, Santello and Soechting, 2000), and muscle
78 activation recordings (Maier and Hepp-Reymond, 1995, Weiss and Flanders, 2004, Tanzarella
79 et al., 2021). These studies demonstrate that a small set of low-dimensional components can
80 account for a wide range of hand movements. This has also been observed at the neuronal level,
81 where synaptic inputs largely shared across spinal motor neurons, particularly in extrinsic hand
82 muscles (Hockensmith et al., 2005, Winges and Santello, 2004), are thought to underlie this
83 modular control (Keen and Fuglevand, 2004, Hockensmith et al., 2005, Winges and Santello,
84 2004, Johnston et al., 2005, Tanzarella et al., 2021). For example, Hockensmith et al. (2005)
85 reported a high degree of commonality in motor unit discharge times between two extrinsic
86 hand muscles acting on the thumb and index finger. Interestingly, this between-muscle
87 commonality was as pronounced as that observed in motor units within individual muscles.
88 However, it remains less clear how the nervous system modulates these common synaptic
89 inputs across different hand movements, particularly when comparing a frequently used grip,
90 such as grasping, with a less functionally relevant hand action, like the simultaneous flexion of
91 all four fingers without involvement of the thumb.

92
93 In this study, we sought to assess the common synaptic oscillations to spinal motor neurons of
94 the extrinsic finger flexor muscles during three tasks: simultaneous flexion of the
95 metacarpophalangeal joints of four fingers without involvement of the thumb (hereafter
96 referred to as four-finger flexion), thumb flexion, and simultaneous flexion of both fingers and
97 thumb (hereafter referred to as grasping). To achieve this, we decomposed motor unit spike
98 trains from high-density surface electromyograms (HDsEMG) recorded from the superficial
99 extrinsic finger flexors and tracked motor units across tasks. We then used coherence analysis
100 to estimate the shared synaptic oscillations in the delta, alpha, and beta bands. Our results

101 revealed a reduction in alpha band oscillations during grasping compared to four-finger flexion.
102 This reduction in alpha band oscillations was reflected in force oscillations, revealing
103 decreased force-neural drive coupling within the alpha band and increased force steadiness
104 during grasping. These findings suggest that a more natural, functionally relevant grip involves
105 specific neural control mechanisms to enhance force control.

106 **Methods**

107 *Participants*

108 Seventeen healthy individuals (5 females; mean \pm standard deviation: age 30 ± 4 years) with
109 no history of upper limb injuries volunteered to participate in this study. Before starting the
110 experiments, all participants provided written informed consent. The experimental procedures
111 received approval from the local ethics committee at the University of Brescia (code NP5665)
112 and were conducted in accordance with the latest version of the Declaration of Helsinki.

113

114 *Experimental protocol*

115 The study comprised a single experimental session lasting approximately 1.5 hrs. Participants
116 were seated comfortably in a chair with their right forearm supported on a custom-built device
117 which was secured to the testing table (**Figure 1A**). The elbow was flexed at 45° (0° being the
118 anatomical position), and the wrist was positioned neutrally (i.e., midway between full
119 supination and full pronation). Both the forearm and wrist were secured to the device with
120 Velcro straps. The four fingers were aligned with the forearm (i.e., pointing forward), and the
121 thumb was held in a mid-flexed position. The distal segments of the thumb and fingers were
122 fixed to adjustable supports attached to the load cells (thumb: SM-100 N; fingers: SM-500 N,
123 Interface, Arizona, USA) to record the isometric forces produced by simultaneous flexion of
124 the four fingers and thumb, either separately or simultaneously (**Figure 1A**).

125

126

127 **Figure 1: Experimental setup and protocol.** A, positioning of participants to perform the experimental task. The
 128 distal segments of the fingers and the thumb were fixed to adjustable supports attached to load cells to measure
 129 isometric forces produced by simultaneous flexion of the four fingers and thumb, either separately or
 130 simultaneously. Two high-density grids of 64 electrodes each were used to record the muscle activity from the
 131 superficial extrinsic flexor muscles of the hand (top panel). B, participants performed maximal voluntary
 132 isometric contractions (MVC) of four-finger and thumb flexion (top), followed by isometric force-matching
 133 contractions (bottom) involving three different tasks: simultaneous flexion of the four fingers without involvement
 134 of the thumb (i.e., four-finger flexion), thumb flexion, and simultaneous flexion of both fingers and thumb (i.e.,
 135 grasping). For each movement, two force levels were performed, 5% and 15% MVC. Visual feedback was
 136 provided as a two-dimensional coordinate plane, where the x- and y-axis corresponded to the flexion forces of
 137 the four-fingers and thumb, respectively, and a green square indicated the target.

138

139 Initially, participants performed maximal voluntary isometric contractions (MVCs) for 3 s,
 140 with a 2 min interval of rest in between. Two MVCs of finger flexion and two MVCs of thumb
 141 flexion were performed in a randomized order (top panel of **Figure 1B**). For each action, the
 142 highest value from the two MVCs was considered the maximal isometric force and used as a
 143 reference for subsequent submaximal contractions. Participants were then instructed to perform
 144 six isometric force-matching contractions involving three different tasks: simultaneous flexion
 145 of the four fingers without involvement of the thumb (i.e., four-finger flexion), thumb flexion,
 146 and simultaneous flexion of all fingers with the thumb (i.e., grasping). For each task,
 147 participants performed two steady isometric contractions at two target forces: 5% and 15%
 148 MVC. Visual feedback of the produced forces was provided as a moving red square in a two-

149 dimensional coordinate plane, where the x- and y-axis corresponded to the forces of four-finger
150 flexion and thumb flexion, respectively, and a green square indicated the target (bottom panel
151 of **Figure 1B**). Participants were required to sustain the force at the target level for 50 s within
152 a tolerance of $\pm 5\%$, indicated by the borders of the green square. During the individual
153 movements (four-finger or thumb flexion), the force acquired by the uninvolved load cell was
154 recorded but not displayed on the monitor. The computer monitor displaying the target and
155 produced forces was positioned ~ 60 cm in front of the participant.

156

157 *Data collection*

158 For all tasks, HDsEMG were recorded in monopolar mode from the superficial extrinsic flexor
159 muscles of the hand using two grids of 64 electrodes each (GR08MM1305; 8 mm inter-
160 electrode distance; OT Bioelettronica, Turin, Italy; **Figure 1A**). To cover as much of the
161 surface area of the muscles as possible, the electrodes were positioned from proximal to distal
162 over the volar surface of the forearm (**Figure 1A**). Before electrode placement, the skin was
163 shaved and mildly abraded (EVERI, Spes Medica, Genova, Italy), and the surface was cleaned
164 with water. The electrode grids were then fixed to the skin using a double-sided adhesive foam,
165 and a conductive paste (AC cream, Spes Medica, Genova, Italy) was used to fill the wells in
166 the foam to ensure optimal electrode-skin contact. A strap electrode dampened with water was
167 used as a reference electrode and positioned on the involved wrist. HDsEMG were sampled at
168 2048 Hz using a 16-bit amplifier (10-500 Hz bandwidth; Quattrocento, OT Bioelettronica,
169 Turin, Italy). Force output from the load cell was amplified by a variable factor (MISO II, OT
170 Bioelettronica) and sampled synchronously with HDsEMG.

171

172 *Data analysis*

173 Data were analyzed offline using MATLAB custom-written scripts (version 2022b, The
174 MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA).

175

176 *Identification and tracking of motor units.* The monopolar HDsEMG were bandpass filtered
177 between 20 and 500 Hz using a 3rd order Butterworth filter. The filtered signals were then
178 visually inspected, and channels with artifacts or contact problems were excluded.
179 Subsequently, the HDsEMG from each electrode grid were decomposed separately into motor
180 unit spike trains using a convolutive blind-source separation algorithm (**Figure 2A**) (Negro et
181 al., 2016). This algorithm has been validated previously (Negro et al., 2016) and widely applied
182 in the literature to assess single motor unit activity in upper limb muscles (Kapelner et al.,
183 2018, Maillet et al., 2022, Cabral et al., 2024a). Missing or misidentified motor unit pulses
184 were iteratively edited by an expert operator, followed by the re-estimation of motor unit spike
185 trains (Martinez-Valdes et al., 2017, Hug et al., 2021). After motor unit editing, the motor units
186 were tracked between four-finger flexion and grasping tasks, as well as between thumb flexion
187 and grasping tasks, by reapplying the motor unit separation vectors from one contraction to the
188 other, and vice-versa (Oliveira and Negro, 2021, Rossato et al., 2022, Cabral et al., 2024a). The
189 motor unit separation vectors are distinct for each individual motor unit and serve as spatio-
190 temporal matched filters to estimate motor unit spike trains. Consequently, the same motor
191 units were analyzed across four-finger flexion and grasping tasks, as well as between thumb
192 flexion and grasping tasks. **Figure 2B** shows examples of the innervation pulse trains (i.e.,
193 motor unit discharge times) and the two-dimensional representations of the motor unit action
194 potentials of motor units tracked between tasks. For each matched motor unit, the instantaneous
195 discharge rate was obtained as the multiplicative inverse of the interspike intervals, and the
196 average value over the 50-s steady force was calculated (i.e., mean discharge rate) and retained
197 for further analysis. It is important to note that common units from both the proximal and distal

198 electrode grids were identified, and the one with the highest coefficient of variation of the
 199 interspike interval was removed from the analysis. Motor unit spike trains were considered to
 200 be generated by the same motor unit if they had at least 30% of common discharge times (Negro
 201 et al., 2016).
 202

203
 204 **Figure 2: Data analysis.** A, high-density surface electromyograms acquired during four-finger flexion (red),
 205 thumb flexion (green), and grasping (blue) were decomposed into motor unit spike trains using a convolutive
 206 blind source separation algorithm (Negro et al., 2016). Raster plots of decomposed motor units for each task are
 207 shown. Note that, for visualization purposes, the raster plots are shown for the last 10 s of the task (yellow boxes).
 208 B, motor units were tracked between tasks by reapplying the motor unit separation vectors from one contraction
 209 to the other, and vice-versa, so the same motor units were analyzed across four-finger flexion and grasping, as
 210 well as between thumb flexion and grasping. Examples of the innervation pulse trains (i.e., motor unit discharge
 211 times) and the two-dimensional representations on twenty selected single-differential channels of the motor units
 212 tracked between tasks are shown.

213
 214 **Estimates of common synaptic oscillations.** Coherence analysis between motor unit spike trains
 215 was used to estimate common synaptic oscillations to spinal motor neurons (Negro and Farina,
 216 2012, Castronovo et al., 2015, Cabral et al., 2024a, Cabral et al., 2024b). Due to the low number
 217 of matched motor units between thumb flexion and grasping tasks (see *Results*), only matched
 218 motor units between four-finger flexion and grasping were included in this analysis.
 219 Specifically, two equally-sized cumulative spike trains (CSTs), obtained as the sum of binary

220 discharge times from randomly selected motor units, were used to calculate the coherence.
221 Each CST comprised half of the total number of matched motor units, with this process
222 repeated up to 100 random permutations (Cabral et al., 2024b). Only participants with at least
223 four matched motor units were included in the coherence analysis (Cabral et al., 2024a). For
224 each interaction, coherence was estimated between the two detrended CSTs using Welch's
225 periodogram with 95% overlapping Hanning windows of 1 s. This analysis was performed over
226 a 30-s time window during the steady contraction, which was selected to maximize the number
227 of active motor units (Maillet et al., 2022).

228 The obtained coherence values were averaged across interactions (i.e., pooled
229 coherence) and z-transformed as previously described (Gallet and Julien, 2011). Only values
230 higher than the bias, defined as the mean value of z-scores between 250 and 500 Hz
231 (Castronovo et al., 2015, Maillet et al., 2022), were considered for further analysis. To assess
232 changes between four-finger flexion and grasping tasks, the area under the curve of the z-
233 coherence was calculated separately for the delta (1-5 Hz), alpha (5-15 Hz) and beta (15-35
234 Hz) bands. Then, the area under the curve ratio (grasping/four-finger flexion) was computed
235 and 1 was subtracted (Cabral et al., 2024a). Thus, ratio values higher than and lower than 0
236 indicated, respectively, increases and decreases in z-coherence during grasping compared with
237 the four-finger flexion task.

238

239 *Coupling between neural drive and force oscillations.* Force signals were initially low-pass
240 filtered using a 3rd order Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of 15 Hz. To assess potential
241 changes in the coupling between neural drive and force oscillations when comparing four-
242 finger flexion and grasping tasks, coherence was calculated between the neural drive and force
243 signals (Negro et al., 2009, Cabral et al., 2024b). The neural drive to the superficial extrinsic
244 flexor muscles of the hand was estimated as the CST of all identified motor units (Thompson

245 et al., 2018). Similar to the analysis of common synaptic inputs, the area under the curve ratio
246 (grasping/four-finger flexion) of z-coherence was calculated to evaluate changes between four-
247 finger flexion and grasping tasks, but focusing only on the frequency bandwidths relevant for
248 force production (i.e., delta and alpha bands; (Cabral et al., 2024b)). Additionally, to quantify
249 alterations in the force steadiness between tasks, we measured the coefficient of variation of
250 force.

251

252 *Statistical analysis*

253 All statistical analyses were conducted in R (version 4.3.0) within the RStudio environment
254 (version 2023.03.1).

255

256 Linear mixed-effect models (LMM) were used to compare the mean discharge rate between
257 four-finger or thumb flexion and grasping tasks, separately for each force level (5% and 15%
258 MVC). This statistical approach accounts for the hierarchical nature of motor unit data,
259 recognizing the non-independence of observations (Tenan et al., 2014), and allows for the
260 inclusion of all matched motor units rather than a single mean value for each participant.
261 Random intercept models were used with ‘task’ as the fixed effect and ‘participant’ as the
262 random effect. LMMs were implemented using the *lmerTest* package (Kuznetsova et al., 2017)
263 with the Kenward-Roger method employed to approximate the degrees of freedom and
264 estimate the *P*-values. The *emmeans* package was applied to determine estimated marginal
265 means and their differences with 95% confidence intervals (Lenth et al., 2019).

266

267 To compare estimates of common synaptic inputs (i.e., z-coherence between motor unit spike
268 trains) and CST-force coupling between four-finger flexion and grasping tasks, changes in the
269 area under the curve ratio (grasping/four-finger flexion) were statistically tested using one-

270 sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test (null hypothesis; $\mu_0 = 0$), separately for each frequency
271 bandwidth. Additionally, to compare the coefficient of variation of force between four-finger
272 flexion and grasping tasks, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were used separately for each force
273 level.

274

275 The effect sizes, along with their 95% confidence intervals, are reported for all the results. For
276 the results of motor unit mean discharge rate, effect sizes were calculated using the *eff_size*
277 function in R, which estimates Cohen's d directly from the outputs of the *emmeans* package.
278 For the area under the curve ratio results, effect sizes were calculated using Cohen's d_s as
279 reported in Jané et al. (2024). For the coefficient of variation of force results, effect sizes were
280 calculated using Cohen's d_z as reported in Jané et al. (2024).

281

282 For the results of motor unit mean discharge rate, the values in the text are reported as mean
283 with 95% confidence intervals. All the other values are reported as median/interquartile ranges
284 unless indicated otherwise. All individual data on matched motor unit discharge times are
285 available at <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28923704>.

286 **Results**

287 *Motor unit identification and mean discharge rate*

288 To compare changes in the mean discharge rate of motor units between four-finger or thumb
289 flexion and grasping tasks, we decomposed HDsEMG from the superficial extrinsic flexor
290 muscles of the hand. For 5% MVC, 20 ± 8 motor units were identified per participant during
291 four-finger flexion, 12 ± 9 during thumb flexion, and 19 ± 7 during the grasping task. For 15%
292 MVC, 22 ± 8 motor units per participant during four-finger flexion, 12 ± 9 during thumb
293 flexion, and 22 ± 8 during grasping were identified. Then, the identified motor units between
294 tasks were tracked to ensure the same units were analyzed. For 5% MVC, 9 ± 6 units were
295 matched between four-finger flexion and grasping tasks, and 2 ± 2 units between thumb flexion
296 and grasping tasks. For 15% MVC, these numbers were 10 ± 8 between four-finger flexion and
297 grasping, and 2 ± 4 between thumb flexion and grasping.

298

299 Significant reductions in motor unit mean discharge rate were observed between four-finger
300 flexion and grasping tasks for both force levels. For 5% MVC, the mean discharge rate
301 decreased from 12.7 [11.8, 13.5] to 12 [11.1, 12.8] pps (LMM, $F = 9.15$, $P = 0.003$, Cohen's d
302 $= -0.35$ [-0.59, -0.11]), and for 15% MVC, from 14.5 [13.4, 15.5] to 13.6 [12.5, 14.6] pps
303 (LMM, $F = 18.64$, $P < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = -0.47$ [-0.72, -0.24]). Conversely, the mean discharge
304 rate significantly increased between thumb flexion and grasping tasks for both 5% MVC (from
305 11.5 [10.3, 12.7] to 13.2 [12, 14.4] pps; LMM, $F = 14.38$, $P < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 0.89$ [0.36,
306 1.43]) and 15% MVC (from 12.6 [11.6, 13.6] to 13.6 [12.5, 14.6] pps; LMM, $F = 4.16$,
307 $P = 0.045$, Cohen's $d = 0.48$ [0.04, 1]) force levels.

308

309 *Estimates of common synaptic inputs*

310 To investigate changes in common synaptic inputs, we calculated the z-coherence between
311 motor unit spike trains. The ratio of the area under the curve was then quantified separately for
312 the delta (1-5 Hz), alpha (5-15 Hz) and beta (15-35 Hz) bands. For this analysis, only matched
313 motor units between four-finger flexion and grasping tasks were utilized, as very few units
314 were matched between thumb flexion and grasping. Additionally, only participants with at least
315 four matched motor units were included. Consequently, coherence analysis was performed for
316 12 and 11 participants for 5% and 15% MVC, respectively. **Figure 4** displays the pooled z-
317 coherence for all participants and the area under the curve ratio results. For both 5% MVC (top
318 panel) and 15% MVC (bottom panel) force levels, there was a clear decrease in the area under
319 the curve in the alpha band (yellow area) for the grasping task (blue) compared to the four-
320 finger flexion task (red). For 5% MVC, a significant median decrease of ~15% was observed
321 in the area under the curve within the alpha band (**Figure 3A**; one-sample Wilcoxon signed-
322 rank test, $P = 0.009$, Cohen's $d_s = -0.81$ [-1.45, -0.14]), but no significant changes were found
323 for the delta (one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $P = 0.622$, Cohen's $d_s = 0.20$ [-0.38, 0.77])
324 or beta bands (one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $P = 1.000$, Cohen's $d_s = 0.01$ [-0.56,
325 0.58]). Similarly, for 15% MVC, the area under the curve within the alpha band for the grasping
326 task was significantly decreased compared to the four-finger flexion task by a median of ~22%
327 (**Figure 3B**; one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $P = 0.032$, Cohen's $d_s = -0.87$ [-1.56, -
328 0.16]), with no significant changes in the delta (one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $P =$
329 0.700 , Cohen's $d_s = 0.20$ [-0.41, 0.79]) or beta bands (one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test,
330 $P = 0.700$, Cohen's $d_s = 0.08$ [-0.52, 0.67]).

331

332

333 **Figure 3: Motor unit coherence results.** The left panel shows pooled z-coherence profiles including all
 334 participants for 5% MVC (A) and 15% MVC (B). Red and blue traces denote four-finger flexion and grasping
 335 tasks, respectively. The horizontal dashed line indicates the confidence level of coherence. Vertical dashed lines
 336 highlight the three frequency bandwidths analyzed: delta (1–5 Hz), alpha (5–15 Hz), and beta (15–35 Hz).
 337 Yellow boxes denote statistical differences in the area under the curve between four-finger flexion and grasping
 338 tasks. The right panel displays group results of the area under the curve ratio of coherence for 5% MVC (top)
 339 and 15% MVC (bottom). Circles identify individual participants. Vertical black traces, boxes, and whiskers denote
 340 the median value, interquartile interval, and distribution range, respectively. * $P < 0.05$.

341

342 **Coupling between neural drive and force oscillations**

343 To determine if the observed changes in the alpha band of common synaptic inputs between
 344 the four-finger flexion and grasping tasks were accompanied by alterations in the linear
 345 coupling between the neural drive and the force oscillations, we calculated the z-coherence
 346 between the CST and the force signals. For this analysis, only the bandwidths relevant to force
 347 production were examined (delta and alpha bands). For both 5% MVC (**Figure 4A**) and 15%
 348 MVC (**Figure 4B**) force levels, significant decreases in the CST-force z-coherence during the
 349 grasping task were observed within the alpha band (one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test; 5%
 350 MVC: $P = 0.043$, Cohen's $d_s = -0.55$ [-1.15, -0.07]; 15% MVC: $P = 0.032$, Cohen's $d_s = -0.97$
 351 [-1.68, -0.23]), with no significant changes for the delta band (one-sample Wilcoxon signed-

352 rank test; 5% MVC: $P = 0.519$, Cohen's $d_s = 0.20$ [-0.41, 0.79]; 15% MVC: $P = 0.102$, Cohen's
 353 $d_s = -0.49$ [-1.11, 0.15]).

354

355

356 **Figure 4: Results of force steadiness and coherence between neural drive and force oscillations.** A-B, left panel
 357 shows pooled z-coherence profiles between the motor units cumulative spike train (CST) and force for 5% MVC
 358 (A) and 15% MVC (B). Red and blue traces denote the four-finger flexion and grasping tasks, respectively. The
 359 horizontal dashed line indicates the confidence level of coherence. Vertical dashed lines highlight the two
 360 frequency bandwidths analyzed: delta (1–5 Hz) and alpha (5–15 Hz) bands. Note that the frequency bandwidth
 361 analyzed was limited to the frequency bandwidth of force. The right panel shows group results of the area under
 362 the curve ratio of z-coherence for 5% MVC (top) and 15% MVC (bottom). Circles identify individual participants.
 363 Vertical black traces, boxes, and whiskers denote the median value, interquartile interval, and distribution range,
 364 respectively. C, group results of the coefficient of variation of force (force steadiness) for 5% MVC (top) and 15%
 365 MVC (bottom). Coloured circles and horizontal grey lines indicate individual participants. * $P < 0.05$.

366

367 To assess changes in force steadiness between four-finger flexion and grasping tasks, we
 368 calculated the coefficient of variation of force. Significant reductions in the coefficient of
 369 variation of force were observed between the four-finger flexion and grasping tasks for 5%
 370 MVC (**Figure 4C**; Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $P = 0.009$, Cohen's $d_z = -0.41$ [-0.90, 0.09]), but
 371 not for 15% MVC; Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $P = 0.854$, Cohen's $d_z = -0.11$ [-0.58, 0.37])
 372 force level.

373 **Discussion**

374 The main purpose of this study was to investigate changes in common synaptic inputs to spinal
375 motor neurons between a functionally relevant and frequently used grip (grasping) and a less
376 functionally relevant hand task (four-finger flexion without thumb involvement). Our results
377 demonstrated a reduction in alpha band (5–15 Hz) oscillations during grasping compared to
378 the four-finger flexion task. These differences were reflected in force oscillations, revealing
379 decreased force-neural drive coupling within the alpha band and increased force steadiness
380 during grasping. These findings suggest that a more functionally relevant and natural grip
381 involves specific neural control mechanisms to enhance force control.

382

383 Considering the complex biomechanical and neural structure of the hand, even frequently
384 performed daily tasks, such as grasping an object, require precise coordination of multiple
385 degrees of freedom that must be controlled simultaneously (Fuglevand, 2011, Santello et al.,
386 2013). Over the past three decades, researchers have sought to understand how the fine
387 coordination of multiple hand muscles is achieved during finger and hand movements
388 (Schieber, 1990, Kilbreath and Gandevia, 1994, Santello and Soechting, 2000, Keen and
389 Fuglevand, 2004, Hockensmith et al., 2005, Tanzarella et al., 2021). As reviewed by Schieber
390 (1990), two (non-mutually exclusive) models describe how descending pathways may be
391 organized to achieve this control. In the first model, each muscle or digit is controlled
392 individually, with corticospinal pathways projecting separately to each motor neuron pool. In
393 the second model (proposed as model 3 in Schieber (1990)), a small set of muscle activity
394 patterns, or synergies, generate the full repertoire of hand movements, with corticospinal
395 pathways diverging across individual motor neuron pools within and across muscles.
396 Compelling evidence from force (Li et al., 1998, Reilly and Hammond, 2000, Santello and
397 Soechting, 2000), kinematic (Soechting and Flanders, 1997, Santello et al., 1998, Santello et

398 al., 2002), muscle activation (Maier and Hepp-Reymond, 1995, Weiss and Flanders, 2004,
399 Tanzarella et al., 2021), and motor unit (Hockensmith et al., 2005, Tanzarella et al., 2021,
400 Wings and Santello, 2004) recordings suggest that the latter model likely exemplifies hand
401 control, with the synaptic inputs that are shared across spinal motor neurons playing a key
402 functional role in grip force coordination (Santello and Fuglevand, 2004). However, the degree
403 of commonality across motor units within and between hand muscles appears to be muscle-
404 and task-dependent. For instance, while extrinsic hand muscles show a significant degree of
405 common synaptic inputs between motor units, some suggest that intrinsic hand muscles exhibit
406 lower commonality (Winges and Santello, 2004, Hockensmith et al., 2005, McIsaac and
407 Fuglevand, 2008, Gandevia and Rothwell, 1987). Interestingly, in the current study it was
408 demonstrated that grip type – highly functional (grasping) versus less frequently performed
409 (four-finger flexion) – also modulates common synaptic inputs across motor units of the
410 superficial extrinsic flexor muscles of the hand. Specifically, we observed a reduction in alpha
411 band coherent oscillations between tracked motor units during grasping compared to four-
412 finger flexion (**Figure 3**).

413

414 Although the physiological basis of the reduction in alpha band oscillations during grasping
415 remains challenging to pinpoint, several potential mechanisms could explain this finding. First,
416 the addition of thumb flexion alongside four-finger flexion (i.e., grasping) compared to four-
417 finger flexion alone may introduce an additional source of common synaptic input to spinal
418 motor neurons, leading to a reduction in alpha band coupling. This hypothesis aligns with
419 previous evidence that reported when a new common input is introduced independently to a
420 motor neuron pool, it can decorrelate motor unit spike train output within specific frequency
421 bands (Negro and Farina, 2011). Second, previous studies suggested that spinal interneurons
422 may phase-cancel cortical oscillatory inputs in the alpha frequency range, thereby reducing

423 force tremor, which subsequently enhances movement precision (Williams et al., 2010, Koželj
424 and Baker, 2014, Cabral et al., 2024a). This mechanism could contribute to improved force
425 control in grasping, which is a more frequently used movement compared to four-finger
426 flexion. Finally, given that modulations in the gain of the Ia afferent feedback loop can directly
427 influence alpha band inputs (Halliday and Redfearn, 1956, Lippold, 1971, Christakos et al.,
428 2006, Laine et al., 2016), it is possible that grasping involves a reduction in Ia afferent gain.
429 Since grasping is more frequently performed in daily life, it may rely less on afferent feedback
430 compared to a less applied and less functional grip. Nevertheless, it remains possible that more
431 complex neural mechanisms are involved, integrating both cortical and spinal pathways.

432

433 Our findings have directly applied relevance, as the observed reductions in alpha band
434 oscillations during grasping were reflected in force fluctuations. Since alpha band fluctuations
435 in the effective neural drive to the muscle are not fully canceled by the muscle's twitch
436 contractile properties, which act as a low-pass filter with a cutoff frequency of ~12 Hz (Bawa
437 and Stein, 1976, Baldissera et al., 1998), they are consequently transmitted to force,
438 contributing to its variability (Negro et al., 2009, Farina et al., 2014). Thus, the reduction in
439 alpha band coherence during grasping may represent a neural strategy to enhance force
440 steadiness in a frequently performed hand task, effectively filtering out frequency oscillations
441 from the control signal responsible for force modulation (i.e., delta band coherence) (Farina et
442 al., 2014, Hug et al., 2023). Supporting this interpretation, the observed decrease in the
443 coefficient of variation of force (indicative of increased force steadiness) during grasping with
444 respect to four-finger flexion at low force levels (**Figure 4C**). This was further supported by a
445 decrease in alpha band coupling between the cumulative spike train and force during grasping
446 compared to four-finger flexion (**Figure 4A and 4B**). These results align with previous studies
447 and support the findings that various factors, such as sensorimotor integration (Laine et al.,

448 2014), muscle contractile properties (Cabral et al., 2024b), pain (Yavuz et al., 2015), or
449 learning a new motor skill (Cabral et al., 2024a), modulate the alpha band in the common
450 synaptic input to motor neurons, directly influencing optimal force control. Therefore, our
451 findings extend this evidence by demonstrating that grip type affects common synaptic
452 oscillations to spinal motor neurons, further influencing force regulation in functionally
453 relevant tasks.

454

455 While these experiments do not allow us to directly address this question, a key issue arising
456 from the findings in this study is whether the observed modulation in common synaptic inputs
457 reflects a hard-wired neural control strategy or emerges due to task constraints (i.e., soft-
458 assembled control), which is a topic of ongoing debate in the literature (Tresch and Jarc, 2009,
459 Kutch and Valero-Cuevas, 2012, Deroncourt et al., 2025). Recently, using a combination of
460 kinematic, electromyography, and functional magnetic resonance imaging data, Leo et al.
461 (2016) demonstrated that human motor cortical areas encode hand movement synergies,
462 supporting the idea that modular hand control is represented at higher motor centers. Similarly,
463 Takei et al. (2017) reported that modular control of hand movements is implemented at the
464 spinal level in primates, suggesting that the nervous system organizes motor outputs into
465 functional modules to simplify the control of voluntary hand movements. In addition to this
466 evidence, given that grasping is an innate reflex in infants, which later develops into voluntary
467 grasping (Dennis, 1943, Twitchell, 1965), it seems to follow that modulation of common
468 synaptic oscillations observed in this study may be embedded in the neural circuitry. However,
469 further research is needed to validate this hypothesis.

470

471 A final consideration regarding differences in motor unit mean discharge rates. This study
472 reported a reduction in mean discharge rate during grasping compared to four-finger flexion

473 alone, though with relatively small effect sizes (see Results). Given the complexity of intrinsic
474 and extrinsic muscle coordination required for hand control, some motor units within the
475 extrinsic flexor muscles primarily contribute to force production, while others play a role in
476 force distribution across muscles and mechanical stabilization (Li, 2002, Kinoshita et al., 1995,
477 Butler et al., 2005). Therefore, the observed small reduction in mean discharge rate may reflect
478 mechanical adaptations rather than direct changes in neural control. Notably, this decrease was
479 contrasted by an increase in mean discharge rate when the thumb was flexed alone compared
480 to grasping. This suggests that the nervous system dynamically adjusts motor unit activity,
481 whether for force generation or mechanical stabilization, to maintain the required force target
482 across different grip conditions.

483

484 In conclusion, the findings of this study demonstrate that grasping, which is a functionally
485 relevant and habitually performed hand movement, exhibits distinct neural control mechanisms
486 compared to less commonly used grips. Therefore, the reduction in alpha band oscillations
487 during grasping suggests a task-dependent modulation of common synaptic input, which has
488 functional implications for enhanced force steadiness and optimized neural drive-force
489 coupling.

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